

Supplementary Information

Enhancement of $0.65\text{Pb}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3-0.35\text{PbTiO}_3$ thick films: Effects of flash lamp annealing

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S1 Annealing temperature modeling - Inside stainless steel substrate

The results of the modeled maximum temperature per pulse 10 μm below the interface between PMN-35PT and stainless steel, as well as at the steel lower surface are given in Fig. S1. The modeling parameters are identical to those in Fig. S1.

Figure S1: Finite element modeling. Maximum temperature per pulse profiles at the PMN-35PT top surface (a, c, e and g) and at the PMN-35PT/steel interface (b, d, f and h) as a function of the number of pulses, the pulse duration, the repetition rate and the energy density, respectively. The values of the fixed parameters for each subfigure are given in the main text. Note the different scales between each row.

S2 Rietveld refinement

Rietveld refinement has been performed for the θ - 2θ scans presented in Fig. 4. The results are shown in Fig. S2, indicating a good match between the calculated and measured data.

Figure S2: θ - 2θ and Rietveld refinement for (a) as-deposited, (b) flash lamp annealed and (c) conventionally annealed PMN-35PT thick films.